

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to another regular issue in 2018 with high quality contributions. This is only possible due to the increasing interest in publishing in our journal and the great support of the community and stakeholders. In particular, I want gratefully thank the authors for their topical and very sound research reported in J.UCS, and the editorial board for careful selection and helpful comments for further improvements.

In the third regular issue of 2018, I am very pleased to introduce six accepted papers from authors from six different countries and four continents.

Fernando Ferri, Arianna D'Ulizia and Patrizia Grifoni from Italy outline their analysis of the trends of the scientific production of language evolution models discussing the current developments and outlines the most promising future perspectives of this research field.

Francois Meyer, Brink van der Merwe and Dirko Coetsee from South Africa discuss their research on a concept embedding model that extends existing word embedding techniques taking time into account by explicitly modelling the time between concept occurrences.

Soto Montalvo, Jesus Palomo and Carmen de la Orden from Spain introduce a complementary teaching tool utilizing artificial intelligence techniques to compile information from different sources and presents only relevant breaking news classified into different subjects and topics, which has been showcased in the finance domain.

In a collaborative research between Brazil and Spain, Giani Petri, Alejandro Calderón, Christiane Gresse von Wangenheim, Adriano F. Borgatto and Mercedes Ruiz report their study analysing the benefits of digital and non-digital games used for SPM education in by focusing on player experience and perceived learning outcome.

Rodrigo Souza, João Lopes, Cláudio Geyer, Anderson Cardozo, Adenauer Yamin and Jorge Barbosa from Brazil discuss their research on the distributed architecture CoIoT for Internet of things applications and findings from a case study in the agricultural area.

In their collaborative research between Chile and USA, Matías Zapata-Barra, Alfonso Rodríguez, Angelica Caro and Eduardo B. Fernández outline their research on BPMN extension and security patterns to advance the software development process with security requirements.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
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